

Replication: Deep Learning for Detecting Cyberbullying Across Multiple Social Media Platforms

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ABSTRACT

Cyberbullying is a type of bullying that is done through digital media and platforms. It includes sending, posting, or sharing negative, harmful, false, or mean content about someone else. In recent studies, deep learning based models have been used in the detection of cyberbullying incidents on social media platforms, claiming that they can overcome the limitations of traditional machine learning models, and improve the performance. Our main focus is to investigate the findings of a recent literature in this regard by reproducing the methods and architectures used and then validating their findings using the same datasets, namely human-labelled data on "attacks" in Wikipedia Talks pages, racism and sexism in Twitter interactions, and bullying in Formspring posts. To achieve this we are recreating the statement and checking the claims made in the previous paper. This way we adapt our code, rather than just trying the old code to work. Unfortunately, our results do not accept the main claim made in the previous paper. Only the Formspring dataset shows a clear performance difference between the best Deep Learning model and the best traditional ML model.

KEYWORDS

Deep Learning, Reproducibility Study, Cyberbullying, Social Media, Neural Networks

1 INTRODUCTION

Cyberbullying has been an issue in online discourse essentially since the inception of the internet. Attempting to detect is not a new endeavour either, but remains a problem that keeps evading its solutions. In this report we detail our efforts to reproduce results by S. Agrawal and A. Awekar in their paper "Deep Learning for Detecting Cyberbullying Across Multiple Social Media Platforms" [1]. The authors kindly provide their code in a GitHub repository, and access to data they used - both in its original, and preprocessed form - as downloads.

This paper made five major claims which are enumerated as: -

- Deep Learning models outperform Traditional ML models in detecting cyberbullying
- Oversampling provides substantially better results
- Word embedding methods do not make a difference to performance
- The performance gap between Deep Learning models is not significant
- Scanning messages for swear words is not a good indicator of cyberbullying

This reproducibility study focuses on verifying the claims and findings of the original authors, adjusting methodology as required on the basis that these claims should stand independent of the Implementation, Platform, and Actors in the study so long as good Data Science principles are followed.

We have also provided our relevant code and notebooks on Github for perusal¹.

2 ISSUES FOUND IN THE ORIGINAL STUDY

In closely scrutinizing the paper and the provided code base, we were able to identify several issues that cast doubt on the overall validity of the claims made in the paper. These issues are outlined below.

2.1 No Tuning of Traditional ML Models

The baseline against which the Deep Learning models are evaluated are the traditional ML models. In their paper, Agrawal and Awekar evaluated Logistic Regression, SVM, Random Forest, and Naive Bayes models using both character 2-grams and word unigrams in TF-IDF form as the data representation method. These models were evaluated with mostly default parameters only with no hyperparameter tuning. In effect, the original authors did not give traditional ML models a fair-go potentially resulting in underperformance of traditional ML. This is explored in section 3.4.1.

2.2 Data Leakage

One of the main findings that were reported was the significant impact of oversampling on the performance of Deep Learning models. Intuitively, this makes sense as the datasets used here are quite imbalanced and there is nothing wrong with the notion in principle. In practice however, the oversampling was done prior to the train/test split, which is a source for major data leakage. In this situation, a model is very likely to train on datapoints that it shouldn't see as it is a duplicate of one in test data. This would thus lead to overfitting which gets more likely as the classes are more imbalanced (and more oversampling occurs). A more realistic look at the impact of oversampling on the performance of these DL models is taken in section 4.2.

2.3 Unfamiliar Architecture for Deep Learning Model

The specific implementation for the CNN model used by Agrawal and Awekar shows a three-branch CNN architecture which is a surprising breakaway from the other models provided which are simple sequential architectures with a single embedding layer and

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¹<https://github.com/Molybdenum42/ExpDesignEx2>

'model' layer. In our implementation, we followed the same simple architecture for the CNN model instead.

3 EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

3.1 Datasets

The experiment uses three datasets, each consisting of the text of a post of a given social media platform, and a manually given label. These datasets come from other specific cyberbullying studies from Formspring[4], Twitter[5], and Wikipedia[6].

3.1.1 Formspring. The Formspring data was originally collected by a paper looking to use traditional ML methods to classify cyberbullying on the Q&A website Formspring.me[4]. The authors scraped the Formspring sites of 18,554 users and randomly kept some posts, creating a corpus of 3,915 posts labelled by Amazon's Mechanical Turk.

In addition to cyberbullying labels, the original data also included a 1-10 scale for severity of cyberbullying as well as words deemed by the applicable Mechanical Turk worker to be indicative of bullying. This additional detail was not used for the purposes of the original paper or this current exercise.

3.1.2 Twitter. The Twitter data comes from a source paper which attempts to identify predictive features on a Twitter dataset using character n-grams methods[5]. This data includes 16,914 tweets from 614 users which have been annotated for racism (1,972 from nine users) and sexism (3,383 from 613 users).

Noting that racist tweets appeared to come from only nine users, and that almost all users in the dataset has made sexist tweets, this dataset is either an indictment on Twitter users, or may not be generally reflective of the social media stage at large. Thus, there may be potential improvements by expanding the corpus of Twitter data being used as a training set.

3.1.3 Wiki. This dataset is taken from a paper which crowd-sourced the labelling of talk pages for discussion on Wikipedia entries and building a labelling classifier to label the remainder of the corpus[6]. This dataset is by far the largest, containing more than 100k human-classified entries, of which the 10 annotators labeled more than 13,500 as personal attacks.

3.2 Data Exploration

As the first step of this study, the data exploration steps were retraced, including simple analysis according to several metrics. It was found that not all the values describing the dataset could be reconstructed such as vocabulary size. For this, no method was found in the original code, and it is unclear where these values are taken from; possibly from the original source of the data.

However, the statistical analysis largely agrees to a good degree, including the attempt to statistically infer the cyberbullying posts by the presence of swearwords according to a list, or the user being anonymous. Refer to section 4.5 for results.

3.3 Platform

The original paper is based on experiments implemented on an unknown operating system using Python 2.7. In this study, Python 3.9 is used instead, which represents the most recent fully functional

release of Python². This change brought several issues with it. Naturally, directly running the code using the newer version of Python was not possible, but fortunately only minor changes - mostly related to print statements - were needed to adjust the syntax to Python 3.

Notably, the preprocessing package no longer exists in the modern version of tensorflow. The same functionality as offered by the vocab_processor function from that package can be implemented using the Tokenizer class from Keras' text preprocessing package, however this highlights one issue in using old tools (which Python 2.7 was in 2018) specifically for the purpose of replicability.

For the sake of clarity, this reproducibility study was done on mixed systems including Windows 10 and Google Colaboratory. All DL results and the AutoML portion of the traditional Machine Learning experiments were done using Google Colaboratory, the rest locally on Windows systems.

3.4 Implementation

3.4.1 Traditional Machine Learning. The exact code of the original version, only slightly modified for Python 3.9, is used together with the pickled, pre-processed data to recreate the exact results reported by Agrawal and Awekar. As can be seen in Table 1, this method led to a wide range of results, ranging from almost identical (for wiki dataset) to huge swings (especially RF and Naive Bayes models). We cannot fully explain this, other than pointing to platform differences discussed in section 3.3. As mentioned in Section 2.1, this implementation does not use any hyperparameter tuning. In an attempt to find better models, an Auto-ML search using autosklearn[3][2] was used and evaluated on a basic holdout test set. These results are considerably closer to the original ones reported in Agrawal:2018, and can be seen compared in Table 2. These values show that there hasn't been improvement, but actually worse performance - likely due to limited training time and very broad search settings.

3.4.2 Word Embeddings. In their paper, Agrawal and Awekar used several methods to initialise word embeddings in the Deep Learning models. The original authors used random initialisations, pre-trained Glove embeddings, and a pretrained SSWE embedding model which doesn't appear to be functional. In our paper, we have random initialisation (by setting an empty Keras Embedding layer), pre-trained Glove embeddings, and pre-trained Word2Vec embeddings as an alternative to SSWE.

Unlike the original paper, the pre-trained embeddings were locked and not trainable which resulted in better Transfer Learning from the pre-trained datasets without the 'fine-tuning' phase. This was due to a worry of overfitting the Embedding layers to rather specific datasets and also to reduce computational load.

3.4.3 DL Architectures. Deep Learning architectures were reproduced in Keras as equivalent Sequential models containing one Embedding layer as an input layer, one 'model' hidden layer (Convolutional, LSTM, or BLSTM) and one fully-connected layer to output the relevant classification. This is then put through a Softmax activation. Dropouts of 0.25 were used (similar to the original

²Technically, at the time of writing (January 2022), Python 3.10 is the most recent release; however, there are many issues still with libraries working with Windows machines

Table 1: Averages of F1-scores across 10-fold CV, with difference to results reported in [1]

Dataset	Label	Character n-grams				Word unigrams			
		LR	SVM	RF	NB	LR	SVM	RF	NB
Formspring	Bully	0.49 (+0.046)	0.48 (+0.061)	0.27 (-0.029)	0.03 (-0.33)	0.49 (+0.001)	0.46 (+0.0)	0.26 (-0.007)	0.03 (+0.0)
	Racism	0.60 (-0.12)	0.76 (+0.083)	0.88 (+0.12)	0.89 (+0.21)	0.69 (-0.052)	0.75 (+0.032)	0.89 (+0.15)	0.88 (+0.26)
Twitter	Sexism	0.62 (-0.11)	0.77 (+0.084)	0.88 (+0.16)	0.90 (+0.25)	0.74 (-0.02)	0.77 (+0.01)	0.90 (+0.14)	0.89 (+0.25)
	Attack	0.70 (+0.009)	0.69 (+0.011)	0.68 (+0.003)	0.67 (+0.012)	0.71 (+0.0)	0.69 (+0.0)	0.73 (+0.0)	0.66 (+0.0)

Table 2: F1-scores³ on test set with Auto-ML model compared to best previous result

Dataset	model	Character n-grams	
		New Score	Original Best
Formspring	extra trees	0.444	0.448
Twitter	sgd	0.718	0.7405
Wiki	sgd	0.661	0.694

Dataset	model	Word unigrams	
		New Score	Original Best
Formspring	extra trees	0.430	0.489
Twitter	random forest	0.727	0.7505
Wiki	sgd	0.654	0.729

paper) in order to reduce the potential for overfitting. An Attention layer was also added after the LSTM layer for the BLSTM with attention model.

Of note is that the CNN architecture was amended from the original three-branch structure to the simpler sequential model mirroring the other architectures used.

3.5 Evaluation Metrics

The Agrawal and Awekar paper used target class f1 score as their evaluation measure. We have opted to use the same measure³ but also provided the confusion matrices of each model in order to get a more holistic look at the performance of the model.

In addition, for the comparison of Deep Learning models, we used McNemar’s Test as a significance test to determine statistical significance in the performance of the models. Our null hypothesis H_0 is that there is no difference in the probabilities of a correct and wrong prediction between any two models being analysed. For the purposes of analysis, we are using a 99% significance level.

4 RESULTS

4.1 Main Claim: Deep Learning Models Outperform Traditional ML Models

The performance of Deep Learning models compared to their traditional ML counterparts is not as clear-cut as the Agrawal and Awekar paper implies. Taking the confusion matrices of the best-performing models from each section (see Figures 1, 2, and 3), we

³For the Twitter dataset - which contains two target classes - the macro-average of the F1-Score for the two target classes is used as a shorthand indicator of performance

can see that outperformance is not so clear-cut as the f1 scores suggest.

Only the Formspring dataset shows a clear performance difference between the best Deep Learning model and the best traditional ML model. The Twitter dataset has very little difference whereas the Wiki data performs better due to the improvement in Precision (having half as many false positives).

Therefore, we conclude that any performance difference is much more nuanced and dataset dependent as the original paper suggests.

4.2 Claim: Oversampling Provides Significantly Better Results

As mentioned in Section 2.2, oversampling in the original paper was conducted prior to the train/test split resulting in substantial data leakage, and hence the claim of significantly better performance with oversampling. On running this again with the correct procedure, there is very little evidence of improvement in results across all datasets, with some cases even showing *reductions* in performance! Table 3 shows an example from the Formspring dataset which showed the best improvements from oversampling; however, as can be seen, there is not much evidence of a significant improvement from oversampling except in very specific model comparisons.

4.3 Claim: Methods to Initialise Word Embeddings do not Make a Difference to Performance

The original claim in the paper was that initial word embedding methods do not have a significant effect on performance when oversampling is done. However, in the table provided by the original authors, one could see little effect on the normally-sampled data as well. However, our own comparison shows that Glove and Word2Vec embedding were far superior in results as compared to a randomly-initialised Embedding layer.

However, it is also worth noting that we have frozen the pre-trained embedding layers, thus making it a Transfer Learning exercise from Glove and Word2Vec.

In Table 4, we show the Wiki dataset which is generally representative of all three. For illustrative purposes, we only show the p-value between Glove and Random as the comparison of Glove and Word2Vec all show p-values above our 1% significance level.

Figure 1: Comparison of Best-Performing Traditional ML and Deep Learning Models in Detecting Cyberbullying - Formspring Data

Figure 2: Comparison of Best-Performing Traditional ML and Deep Learning Models in Detecting Cyberbullying - Twitter Data

Table 3: Comparison of Performance Between Normal and Oversampled Data on the Formspring Dataset

Model (Embedding Method)	f1 (Normal)	f1 (Oversample)	Chi ²	p-value
LSTM (Random)	0.20	0.33	2.87×10^2	1.89×10^{-64}
LSTM (Glove)	0.47	0.49	1.52×10^{-2}	0.902
LSTM (Word2vec)	0.50	0.60	Error	Error
BLSTM (Random)	0.19	0.42	2.78×10^2	2.21×10^{-62}
BLSTM (Glove)	0.53	0.53	0.658	0.417
BLSTM (Word2vec)	0.57	0.55	0.188	0.665
BLSTM w/Attention (Random)	0.41	0.26	12.6	3.77×10^{-4}
BLSTM w/Attention (Glove)	0.48	0.44	0.391	0.532
BLSTM w/Attention (Word2vec)	0.52	0.52	3.52	0.061
CNN (Random)	0.41	0.43	13.8	2.04×10^{-4}
CNN (Glove)	0.42	0.50	0.16	0.689
CNN (Word2vec)	0.54	0.54	7.61	5.82×10^{-3}

Figure 3: Comparison of Best-Performing Traditional ML and Deep Learning Models in Detecting Cyberbullying - Wiki Data

Table 4: Comparison of Performance Between Embedding Methods for the Wiki Dataset

Model	f1 (Random)	f1 (Glove)	f1 (Word2Vec)	Chi ²	p-value (Random vs. Glove)
LSTM	0.06	0.73	0.72	5.21×10^2	2.71×10^{-115}
BLSTM	0.33	0.73	0.72	3.56×10^3	0
BLSTM w/Attention	0.29	0.72	0.73	4.82×10^3	0
CNN	0.60	0.71	0.73	2.45×10^2	3.10×10^{-55}

Table 5: Pairwise McNemar’s Test Comparison between Models Using Glove Embedding for the Twitter Dataset

Model 1	Model 2	Chi ²	p-value
LSTM	BLSTM	1.01	0.316
LSTM	BLSTM w/Attention	0.88	0.348
LSTM	CNN	2.27	0.132
BLSTM	BLSTM w/Attention	0.005	0.944
BLSTM	CNN	0.097	0.755
BLSTM w/Attention	CNN	0.082	0.775

4.4 Claim: The Performance Gap Between DL Models is not Significant

On an intuitive level, this finding seems unexpected as research suggests RNN models like LSTM would generally outperform CNNs except for very specific keyphrase recognition tasks[7]. Our analysis generally confirms this to be the case when proper word embedding is used. As seen in Table 5, there is no statistically-significant difference at a 99% level between all four models using the Glove embedding and this generally applies across all datasets and the Word2Vec as well⁴.

It is worth noting however, that all models tested are relatively simple two or three hidden layer models (one embedding layer plus

⁴A key exception to this is Word2Vec for Twitter where the LSTM and BLSTM models outperformed the BLSTM with Attention and CNN models

the relevant model layer - with the addition of an attention layer for the BLSTM Attention model). This finding should not preclude the fact that better or more sophisticated models exist and can potentially outperform the models we have built here.

4.5 Claim: Scanning Messages for Swear Words is not a Good Indicator of Cyberbullying

Analysis of the frequency of messages with swearwords, and how often those correspond to cyberbullying, gives essentially equivalent results to those reported by Agrawal and Awekar. In this method, a message was considered to contain swearing if any of a list of predetermined swearwords were found in it. Given the limitations of naive string comparisons, this misses e.g. swearwords as part of a composite word: "fuck" and "shit" are obviously swear words, and "fuckshit" would similarly be considered less than polite by most readers, but not found by comparing to either "fuck" or "shit". We have found that using a different method of detecting swearwords, by checking if any of the same predetermined list is contained in the message (which does find composite swearwords) results in a considerably higher rate of swearing $P(S)$, but further reduces the association between swearing and bullying $P(B|S)$, and thus only further supports this finding.

5 DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

In this paper, we attempted to reproduce the results and claims made by Agrawal and Awekar in their paper, i.e. Deep Learning

Table 6: Frequency of swearwords and bullying, original method

Dataset	P(B)	P(S)	P(B S)	P(S B)	P(B A & S)
Formspring	0.06	0.16	0.22	0.59	0.25
Twitter	0.314	0.135	0.43	0.185	
Wiki	0.117	0.165	0.496	0.696	0.653

models outperform traditional Machine Learning models in the detection of cyberbullying. Unfortunately, these results did not appear to be the case, with most of the overperformance of Deep Learning models in the original paper due to data leakage from an incorrectly-split test set during the oversampling phase. In addition, the original writers did not fully tune their traditional Machine Learning models, creating an uneven playing field.

Nonetheless, we did determine that good Word Embeddings are absolutely critical for the performance of Deep Learning models. In addition, for simple Deep Learning models, we found that the type of hidden layer doesn't matter for performance; however, it is very likely that data scientists with more experience in Deep Learning model-building will be able to build an architecture which outperforms these very simple models.

In addition, it must be noted that the data that these models are trained on could be very outdated (Formspring was shut down in 2013, nine years prior to the time of writing) and/or overly specific so as to create doubt regarding the generalisation of the data (the Twitter data seems overly focused on Muslims and Australian cooking show *My Kitchen Rules*). Any future model would benefit significantly from larger and more robust corpus of data.

6 FUTURE WORK

Different adaptations, tests, and experiments have been left for the future due to lack of time and reliable updated data. Future work could be done to do a deeper analysis of the corpus, try different

methods for predicting different types of cyberbullying. A number of recommendations for future research are given below.

1. Statistical testing between traditional machine learning algorithms and deep learning algorithms could be performed further on. This could statistically accept or reject the hypothesis that deep learning performs better than traditional machine learning when detecting different forms of cyberbullying.

2. Create deep learning models with an improved architecture. Due to hardware and time constraints this was not possible in this replication. With additional hardware and time, better architecture can be constructed. Also, it is important to make the architecture scalable and adaptive.

3. Replace current data sources with more update ones. Wording changes with time and cyberbullies change the way they bully overall. Because of this new sources of data would improve the models and their detection of cyberbullying.

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